

Phytochemical Investigation of the Roots of *Camellia sinensis* L. (O. Kuntze)

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Although chemistry of tea constituents has been widely studied over the years¹, not much work has been done with the tea roots². The newly observed anticarcinogenic³ properties of tea roots [*Camellia sinensis* L. (O. Kuntze)] prompted us to examine them. Herein we report for the first time the isolation of tectoquinone, α -spinasterol and its glucoside from the roots of this plant.

Air-dried roots of *C. sinensis* were extracted by percolation with methanol at ambient temperature. After removal of solvent under reduced pressure, the residue was diluted with water and extracted with ethyl acetate. The residue after removal of ethyl acetate on chromatography over silica gel and elution with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)-chloroform (3 : 1) afforded a solid, which was recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 177–78°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 677 (C=O), 1 593 (Ar), 845 and 708 cm^{-1} . $\lambda_{\max}$ (CHCl₃) 327 nm; C₁₅H₁₀O₂, *m/z* (%) 222 [M⁺] (60), 207 [M-CH₃]⁺ (6), 194 [M-CO]⁺ (31), 179 [M-CH₃-CO]⁺ (2), 165 [M-2 CO-H]⁺ (100), 139 [M-CO-H-C₂H₂]⁺ (20), 104 [C₇H₄O]⁺ (4), 89 [C₇H₃]⁺ and 76 [C₆H₄]⁺ (30); pmr δ (CDCl₃, TMS) 2.54 (3H, s, 2-CH₃), 7.62 (1H, br d, *J* 8 Hz, H-3), 7.72–7.92 (2H, m, H-6, H-7), 8.12 (1H, br s, H-1), 8.24 (1H, br d, *J* 8 Hz, H-4), 8.30–8.40 (2H, m, H-5, H-8). The physical data of the compound (ir, uv, pmr and ms and m.p.) are in close agreement with tectoquinone⁴.

Further elution of the column with petroleum ether-chloroform (1 : 1) afforded a sterol, m.p. 168–69°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 530–3 230 (OH), 970 (*trans*-CH=CH-), 845 cm^{-1} (CH=C), C₂₈H₄₈O, (M⁺ 412) which was characterised as α -spinasterol⁵ by usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc, co-ir) with authentic specimen.

Finally, elution of the column with chloroform-methanol (9 : 1) furnished a white solid, which was recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 284–85°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 550–3 150 (OH), 971 (*trans*-CH=CH-), 846 cm^{-1} (CH=C), C₃₅H₅₈O₆ (M⁺ 574). Hydrolysis of the compound afforded a sterol, identified as α -spinasterol, and glucose, identified by pc and glc analysis of its peracetate. The presence of glucose moiety was indicated by pmr spectrum of the glucoside. The comparison of the physical data (m.p., ir, nmr, ms) of the compound with an authentic specimen⁶ confirmed it as 3-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl- α -spinasterol.

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